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H₂O₂ formation and decomposition under PEMWE conditions

Martin Ise*, Baran C. Erer, Elvira Fernandez Sanchis, Markus Ungerer
 Siemens Energy Global GmbH & Co. KG, SE TI SES PRM CD ECH,
 Schuckertstr. 2, 91058 Erlangen/Germany

*Contact corresponding authors: www.EFCF.com/ContactRequest

Abstract

Under polymer electrolyte membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE) conditions, H₂O₂ is an unstable side product. As a reactive species, H₂O₂ can attack materials used in PEMWE systems. Especially, it is harmful for polymer electrolyte membranes in combination with Fenton active cations of metals like Fe. Moreover, some polymer and metal materials are unstable in H₂O₂ solutions. Therefore, it is important to understand the effects caused by H₂O₂ and possibilities for keeping its concentration low.

In order to find a way for reducing the attack of H₂O₂ on PEMWE materials, decomposition mechanisms of H₂O₂ were analyzed. Experiments for catalyst enhanced H₂O₂ decomposition were conducted with Pt and Pd catalyst particles in H₂O₂ solutions. In agreement with literature data, faster initial decomposition of H₂O₂ was found for Pt. As an additional parameter, the effect of electrochemical potential on the decomposition rate will also be discussed.

For effective removal of H₂O₂ out of the PEMWE process water loops, a catalyst bed containing a suitable amount of H₂O₂ decomposition catalyst is needed. In this direction, lab experiments with catalyst coated mesh materials and with a catalyst containing ion exchange resin (DuPont™ AmberTec™ UP4000Pd OH) were conducted. The results of flow through experiments with this ion exchange resin are shown in Fig. 1. Next steps are the optimization of the H₂O₂ decomposition catalyst bed design and stability analyses of the catalyst bed.

Figure 1: H₂O₂ decomposition ratio as function of space velocity in catalyst bed filled with DuPont™ AmberTec™ UP4000Pd OH.

Introduction

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) can form as an undesired byproduct under PEM water electrolysis conditions, which can cause degradation of system components. It is widely considered the main contributor to chemical degradation of the membrane over time, in presence of Fenton active species [1]. Due to its corrosive properties, high concentrations of H₂O₂ in the process water could lead to increased metal dissolution rates from metal components of PEM water electrolyzer plants. Additionally, the ion exchangers that are present in the water loops are chemically less stable in H₂O₂ solutions. Overall, these factors cause a lifetime decrease of PEM water electrolyzer components in the long term.

H₂O₂ and related radical species can be formed during cell operation which can then attack the chemical bonds of perfluoro sulfonic acid membranes leading to chemical degradation either by chain unzipping (by releasing 2 HF_s while shortening the backbone by one CF₂ unit) or by direct scission of side chain chemical bonds. The degree of this process is commonly measured by monitoring fluoride release rates with higher rates being associated with shorter membrane lifetime [2]. This in turn leads to protonic conductivity loss and membrane thinning. Similar phenomena of chemical bond cleavage also apply to the ion-exchange resins, resulting in a reduction of their lifespan.

Significant H₂O₂ concentrations were measured especially in PEMWE cathode water loops. Fig. 2 shows the average H₂O₂ concentrations measured from the cathode water loops of 300 cm² PEM electrolyzer test stands operated by Siemens Energy during over 20 test runs conducted with atmospheric, 10 bar and 35 bar operating pressure, for membranes with and without gas recombination catalysts (GRC).

Figure 2: Averaged measured H₂O₂ concentrations in laboratory test stands from the cathode side water loop at different operating pressures, including standard error bars.

The H₂O₂ concentration in the process water is desired to be lower than 0.1 mg/l, however much higher concentrations were occasionally measured, as indicated by Figure 1. A significant increase in H₂O₂ concentrations with rising operating pressure is evident, with the average of the samples extracted at 35 bar being approximately 4 mg/l. Reaching elevated operating pressures is a desired condition for future generations of PEM water electrolysers, which highlights the importance of investigating ways to achieve H₂O₂ removal from the process water loops. This issue was aimed to be tackled by this study.

1. Literature Study

H₂O₂ is a commodity chemical which is extensively used as an oxidizing agent in various industries such as paper and pulp industry, and in catalytic oxidation processes such as propene oxide synthesis from propene [3-4]. Although in trace amounts, some H₂O₂ is present even in DI water, typically formed as result of the ultraviolet light treatment to remove organic impurities [5]. H₂O₂ presence is undesired in applications that require the use of highest purity water, such as the semiconductor manufacturing or PEMWE, due to its oxidative and corrosive properties. Yano et al. reported that even H₂O₂ concentrations of 10-40 µg/L accelerate copper dissolution rate in water significantly [5], which emphasizes that the effects of H₂O₂ can be strong even at extremely low concentrations.

a) H₂O₂ formation

H₂O₂ can be formed chemically in presence of H₂ and O₂ as reactants by the direct synthesis of hydrogen peroxide (DSHP) process. In PEMWE, this condition may arise due to gas crossover through the membrane. The DSHP reaction proceeds as following [3]:

Pd based catalysts have been extensively studied and have been recognized as the most effective transition metal catalyst for the DSHP reaction by numerous studies, although considered prototypical due to the limited selectivity towards H₂O₂ caused by consecutive H₂O₂ decomposition and hydrogenation reactions [3-4]. Considering that Pt has similar properties to Pd regarding electronegativity and lattice parameters, it would also be expected to show catalytic activity towards DSHP which has been previously demonstrated, even though with less selectivity [6]. Typical state-of-the-art PEMWE cathode catalyst layers are Pt based, and the presence of trace Pt in water at the cathode side is possible due to dissolution or particle detachment. Pt is also incorporated as a GRC in PFSA membranes, particularly in stacks that operate at elevated pressures, to promote H₂ and O₂ recombination to H₂O and limit H₂ cross-over to the anode. This does not mean, however, that the DSHP reaction could be disregarded, which thermodynamically could also occur on the GRC.

H₂O₂ can also be formed electrochemically, either by partial O₂ reduction reaction (Partial ORR) or H₂O oxidation under suitable conditions, which are all theoretically present in a PEMWE cell. Partial ORR and H₂O oxidation reactions proceed as following [7]:

From the given equilibrium half cell potentials it follows that significant electrochemical H₂O₂ formation would be expected only in case of not well performing anodes operating at voltages above 1.763 V, while thermodynamically, such formation is always possible at the cathode.

b) H₂O₂ decomposition

H₂O₂ can be decomposed by several chemical reactions. The most widely known H₂O₂ decomposition mechanism, so called the Fenton reaction has been discovered over 100 years ago by H.J.H. Fenton and denotes the decomposition of H₂O₂ ions homogeneously catalysed by ferrous ions. It is also occurring with other Fenton active ions. The Fenton reaction generates highly reactive OH· radicals as products and is therefore widely utilized in applications such as wastewater treatment that require oxidative destruction of

contaminants. This reaction causes degradation of PFSA membranes by radical attacks and should be avoided in PEMWE cells. The overall reaction proceeds as

Moreover, chemical H₂O₂ decomposition is possible by two reaction equations which do not produce OH· radicals, namely the H₂O₂ disproportionation and hydrogenation reactions [3]. Whether radicals are generated as intermediates depends on the intermediate reactions taking place.

High H₂O₂ disproportionation rates are especially found for platinum group metals. Specific first order reaction rate constants reported for platinum, iridium and palladium are summarized in Table 1 [9-10]. Due to differences in the experimental conditions the results are not identical, but the same order of catalyst efficiency (Pt > Ir > Pd) was found in the two given references.

Table 1: First order specific rate constants of platinum, iridium and palladium for H₂O₂ disproportionation reaction reported in the literature

<i>Catalyst</i>	$k_1 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2})$ [9]	$k_1 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2})$ [10]
Platinum	3.23 x 10 ⁻⁷	6.4 x 10 ⁻⁶
Iridium	1.03 x 10 ⁻⁷	1.2 x 10 ⁻⁶
Palladium	3.67 x 10 ⁻⁸	3.4 x 10 ⁻⁷

Another possible way of H₂O₂ removal is its electrochemical decomposition. This could occur at the electrolysis cell electrodes or possibly by introducing an additional electrochemical cell/stack in the process water loops. This process would involve the utilization of the reverse reactions of the partial ORR and H₂O oxidation reactions described above as electrochemical H₂O₂ formation mechanisms with the same equilibrium potentials [7]:

Considering the concentration of H₂O₂, the equilibrium potentials for the equations above are only valid for standard conditions (1 mol/l H₂O₂). Lowering the H₂O₂ concentration results in an increase of the H₂O₂ oxidation potential resp. a decrease of the H₂O₂ reduction potential of approximately 30 mV per order of magnitude [7]. For a concentration of 1 μmol/l H₂O₂ (34 μg/l), this results in an equilibrium potential of 0.875 V for the H₂O₂ oxidation and an equilibrium potential of 1.583 V for the H₂O₂ reduction. Under PEMWE operation conditions, H₂O₂ oxidation is always expected at the anode and H₂O₂ reduction is always expected at the cathode.

As suggested by Liu et al. [11] an electrochemical cell fed with 0.5 mol/l H₂O₂ (in water with 0.5 mol/l H₂SO₄) at the anode and operating at approximately 1 V could utilize the

H₂O₂ oxidation reaction at the anode and the hydrogen evolution reaction at the cathode with more than 40% faradaic efficiency. However, as was shown by Katsounaros et al. [7] the decomposition of H₂O₂ with an initial concentration of 2·10⁻³ mol/l on a Pt electrode was almost independent of the applied anodic potential in the range of 0.5 - 1.3 V. Therefore, the chemical H₂O₂ decomposition reaction appeared to be the dominant decomposition pathway. For this reason, we focus on chemical H₂O₂ decomposition reactions in the following chapters.

2. Experimental Analyses

a) Measurements of H₂O₂ decomposition by catalyst powders in solution

In order to measure the H₂O₂ decomposition efficiencies of available catalyst powders, palladium black (Heraeus, Type 100-11) and platinum black (Heraeus, Type 600-02) powders were used as catalysts for the kinetic evaluation with the specific surface areas of 25.8 m² /g and 23.5 m² /g respectively. 1 l of H₂O₂ solution with an aimed initial concentration of 17 mg/l was prepared in ultrapure water and the initial concentration was verified. 50 mg of the respective catalyst powder was added in the solution to start the reaction. The solution was stirred at 1000 rpm on a magnetic stirrer throughout the reaction time, at room temperature. Water samples were extracted by filtering through 0.22 micrometer pipette filters. The total reaction time was 1 hour, and the volume of each sample extracted was 10 ml, equal to 1% of the total reaction volume. H₂O₂ concentrations in the samples were measured photometrically using the Supelco™ Spectroquant™ H₂O₂ test (Merck™) immediately after extraction to avoid measuring inaccurate data caused by further self-decomposition of H₂O₂ or possibly by remaining catalyst particles in the sample. The photometric test had a measurement window between 0.015 - 3 mg/l. To measure higher concentrations than 3 mg/l, respective samples were diluted before measurement and the measured concentrations were then adjusted by multiplying with the dilution ratio.

b) Measurements of H₂O₂ decomposition in flow-through setup

Further tests of H₂O₂ decomposition were conducted using a flow-through setup. These tests consisted of the evaluation of the H₂O₂ decomposition by using an ion exchange resin loaded with Pd and on the other hand, the H₂O₂ decomposition by using Pt coated mesh materials. A flow-through setup was constructed in the laboratory for the evaluation of catalysts at varying flow conditions. For the Pd-loaded anion exchange resin DuPont™ AmberTec™ UP4000Pd OH, a fritted glass tube with 10 mm inner diameter was used as a catalyst bed. The bed volume (BV) was 3.7 ml (47 mm bed height). H₂O₂ solutions were fed from the top of the bed, in a top-to-bottom flow configuration. A peristaltic pump was used to adjust the flowrate to the desired value. The solution had no contact with metal components that might also cause rapid H₂O₂ decomposition. A pressure gauge was installed to the inlet of the catalyst bed to evaluate the pressure drop. The setup was not in a loop configuration and separate borosilicate glass reservoirs were used as feed and waste. For analyzing the influence of temperature, the temperature of the H₂O₂ solution feed reservoir was adjusted by a heating plate. The setup was also used for tests with Pt coated mesh materials, these runs were conducted using a polymer cylinder with an inner diameter of 37 mm as the catalyst bed. The bed volume was 13 ml (12 mm bed height) in this case.

3. Results

a) Kinetic evaluation of H₂O₂ decomposition by catalyst powders in solution

The measured H₂O₂ concentrations from the decomposition experiments with catalyst powders are shown in Fig. 3. Assuming first order reaction kinetics and considering the specific surface area of the catalyst, the reaction rates were determined to be $k_{Pt\ Black} = 1.13 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ and $k_{Pd\ Black} = 3.79 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$. Compared to the values obtained by McKee [9], the rate for Pd is similar whereas the rate for Pt is almost by a factor of 3 lower (see Table 1). The higher reaction rate of Pt is in agreement with the literature data; however, it was found that for longer reaction times there was no further decrease of the H₂O₂ concentration in our experiments with Pt catalyst powder in solution, partly explainable by an effect of traces of Pt catalyst in the photometer test. Therefore, decomposition of H₂O₂ in concentrations below 3.5 mg/l must be further investigated for Pt containing solutions.

Figure 3: Decrease of H₂O₂ concentration vs. time curves for Pt black and Pd black.

b) Measurements of H₂O₂ decomposition in flow-through setup

The results of H₂O₂ decomposition in the flow-through measurements with the Pd-loaded anion exchange resin DuPont™ AmberTec™ UP4000Pd OH and 1 mg/l initial H₂O₂ concentration at 60 °C are shown in Fig. 1. The plotted decomposition ratios show a significant effect of the applied space velocity. Compared to a remaining H₂O₂ concentration of 90 ppb at 2323 BV/h, the H₂O₂ concentration is strongly reduced to 40 ppb at 353 BV/h. Even higher H₂O₂ decomposition ratios could be achieved by lowering the space velocity. Further experiments showed that the influence of temperature was moderate (decrease from 91 % decomposition at 60 °C to 84 % at 25 °C for the highest space velocity 2323 BV/h). Additional test runs at 25 °C showed that in the initial H₂O₂ concentration range of 0.5-4 mg/l the results for the decomposition ratio varied only by a few % (for space velocities of 353 and 2323 BV/h). Short term accelerated aging tests with this resin in a solution with 100 mg/l H₂O₂ at 80 °C for 7 h did not show resin aging effects by optical microscopy. However, further testing is necessary to prove sufficient long-term stability of the analyzed material under PEMWE conditions.

Further flow-through experiments were conducted with Pt coated mesh materials. Initial trials with these materials resulted in significantly lower H₂O₂ decomposition ratios compared to the Pd-loaded resin analysis described above. Further analyses including geometrical optimization and long-term testing are necessary in this direction.

4. Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn from the conducted studies:

- H₂O₂ concentrations build up in PEMWE operation, these should be reduced to avoid H₂O₂ attack to the used materials.
- Faster H₂O₂ decomposition was found with Pt black than with Pd black in solution, however, decomposition rates with Pt below 3.5 H₂O₂ mg/l must be further investigated.
- Over 90% H₂O₂ decomposition is possible with DuPont™ AmberTec™ UP4000Pd OH at 60 °C with flow rates up to 2323 BV/h.
- Further analyses are necessary for showing effective applicability and long-term stability of catalyst beds for decomposition of H₂O₂.

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